

INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF MULTIPLE TUNED MASS DAMPERS ON WIND-INDUCED VIBRATIONS IN STEEL TALL BUILDINGS

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ABSTRACT

Steel tall buildings are susceptible to wind-induced vibrations. The lateral displacement and floor accelerations beyond a specific limit will cause discomfort to the people inside the building. The low intrinsic damping in tall buildings is supplemented with damping devices like tuned mass dampers (TMD). Instead of a single large TMD, multiple tuned mass dampers (MTMD) reduce maintenance problems. In this paper, a parametric study has been presented for the optimal distribution of multiple undamped tuned mass dampers arranged in different spatial patterns. The reduction in the lateral displacements and floor accelerations in the along-wind and torsional responses of the buildings are presented. The steel tall buildings are modelled using SAP2000, a general-purpose FE software. The wind velocity fluctuation time histories generated by the NatHaz Modelling Laboratory has been converted to the wind forces and applied on the buildings. The results obtained using undamped MTMDs are compared in the terms of power spectral density, peak values, installation area and efficacy. The horizontal distribution of TMDs in the shape of a cross at the topmost storey has been found to be the efficient configuration for the building with bisymmetric cross-sections. A single TMD placed at the edge of the building brought a significant reduction in the torsional responses. A simple weightage table has been evolved to bring out the relative merits of different MTMD configurations.

Keywords: Multiple tuned mass dampers, wind time history, floor acceleration, area usage

1 INTRODUCTION

An absolute criterion is yet to be derived to define a building as a tall building, as per CTBUH (Council of Tall Buildings and Urban Habitat) (1). The necessity for tall buildings (heights of 50 m – 250m as per IS 16700) (2) is to have more habitation in densely populated cities. From the perspective of structural engineering, tall buildings are slender and flexible structures that are vulnerable to wind-induced lateral movements (3). To alleviate this (i) corner cuts in the building (4) or (ii) supplementary devices like tuned mass dampers (TMD) are introduced. Among many types of external damping systems, the TMD is considered efficient because of its requirement for limited floor area and a higher level of effective damping (5). It is a device that has a mass, a spring and, optionally, a damper attached to the structure to control the dynamic response due to wind by tuning the frequency of the TMD according to the natural frequency of the structure. When the structure is excited at a particular frequency, TMD will produce an out-of-phase response, which counters the structural response (6). Some famous tall buildings with TMDs installed are the CN Tower in Toronto, the Shanghai World Finance Centre in Shanghai and the Taipei Tower in Taiwan (7).

The disadvantages of a single TMD are they operate with one particular frequency, may get detuned over time and need a large lumped mass to be connected to one specific location, typically the

topmost floor of the building (8). Alternatively, multiple TMDs can be tuned to either one single frequency or multiple modes of frequency with a broader bandwidth (9) while the mass gets distributed to different locations of the building, requiring less space installation. This paper presents the effect of undamped multiple-tuned mass dampers (MTMD) placed with different spatial variations in buildings. Two different steel tall buildings are chosen: (a) symmetrical building and (b) unsymmetrical building. It is assumed that the spatial distribution of TMDs requires less space for installation.

2 STUDIES ON EFFECT OF MTMD AGAINST WIND EXCITATIONS

To the author's knowledge, the use of time history of wind loads has been least investigated, possibly due to the complexity of its implementation (10). In this paper, an attempt has been made to use the wind loads as time histories. The development of this framework is very complicated, and hence, a wind spectrum published by NatHaz Modelling Laboratory at the University of Notre Dame, USA, is used in this study (11). The tuned mass dampers are distributed in a vertical direction throughout the height of the building with different variations like (i) uniform variation, (ii) linear variation and (iii) partial installations. In the plan of the topmost storey, TMDs are placed in the form of i) a cross, (ii) along the perimeter and (iii) distributed throughout the topmost storey. The area required and their efficacy in each of the cases are also studied. Each parameter was given a scoring, so that by combining all the scores together, a suitable MTMD configuration could be determined. The distributions of TMDs in vertical and horizontal directions are shown in *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 1. a) Different configurations of distribution of TMDs in the vertical direction in B1
b) Different configurations of distribution of TMDs in the horizontal direction in B1
c) Different configurations of distribution of TMDs in the horizontal direction in B2

3 IMPLEMENTATIONS OF THE TIME HISTORY WIND SPECTRUM

As mentioned in section 2, the time histories for wind loading are generated from the NatHaz online wind simulator (NOWS), which is based on the code ASCE 7-98. Four different simulation schemes of wind velocity fluctuations are provided in the NOWS. Based on a review, the discrete frequency function by introducing FFT and Cholesky decomposition has been chosen. For the present study, the buildings are assumed to be in Chennai, India, where the basic wind speed is considered to be 50 m/s at the height of 10 m from the ground level, with a 3-second gust. The time history is generated for 3600 seconds with a Nyquist frequency of 2 Hz, hence a total number of frequencies being 7200. The urban exposure category of B is chosen. The wind velocity

fluctuations are simulated for every storey height with a total of fifty time histories. The time history of the first and the fiftieth storeys are shown in Fig. 2. The variation in the pattern of fluctuation between the bottom-most and top-most storey can be observed. The wind forces are obtained as per Indian standard code IS 875 (Part 3): 2015.

Fig. 2. a) Wind velocity fluctuations at 3 m b) Wind velocity fluctuation at 150 m

The wind force is calculated every 0.25 seconds by adding the mean wind force and the fluctuating component of the wind. The density of wind is assumed to be 1.2 kg/m³. The wind time histories are applied at specific points, and the tributary area is taken as the product of bay spacing and the height of the stories (5m x 3m = 15m²). A typical wind force time histories for the first and the fiftieth storey has been shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. a) Wind force time history at 3 m b) Wind force time history at 150 m

4 STUDIES ON BUILDINGS WITH MTMD

Two fifty-storey buildings in Chennai are assumed as base models, B1 and B2. They are of plan dimensions 25 m x 25 m and height 150 m (fifty stories of three metres height each). B1 has a core shear wall, and B2 has an eccentric shear wall. The dimensions of the structural elements are mentioned in Table 1. The first natural period of B1 is found to be 3.86 seconds, and that of B2 is 3.80 seconds. The damping ratio of the building is assumed to be 2 per cent of the critical damping. Loading includes the floor finish of 1 kN/m², live load of 2 kN/m² and wall loads of 6 kN/m.

Table 1. Dimensions of structural elements

Element	Dimensions	Grade of material
Column	800x800x32	S355J0H
Primary beam	HE600M	S275JR
Secondary beam	IPE240	S275JR
Wall	400mm thick	C25/30 concrete
Slab	100mm thick	C25/30 concrete

The properties of tuned mass damper such as mass m_s , stiffness k_s , and damping c_s are calculated by Eq (1).

$$m_s = \mu M; \quad k_s = \frac{m_s g}{L}; \quad c_s = 2 \zeta_s m_s \sqrt{\frac{g}{L}} \quad (1)$$

where μ is the mass ratio (ratio between the mass of TMD and the mass of the building), g is the acceleration due to gravity, L is the length of the pendulum, T is the natural period in seconds and ζ_s is the critical damping ratio of TMD (6). The length of the pendulum is dependent on the natural period of the structure to which the TMD is used to prevent the resonance condition, and it is found by Eq (2).

$$L = \left(\frac{T}{2\pi}\right)^2 \times g \quad (2)$$

All the TMDs are tuned in a way to reduce the effect of resonance in the first natural frequency of the building in this research. Initially, a single TMD (B1S0D0) is attached to the top of the building B1. For vertical variations, the TMDs are distributed along the height in a way that every two floors of the building have a TMD (B1VCD0) with a total of 25 TMDs so that the large mass is split into 25 units throughout the building. Each of the TMDs has constant mass and stiffness. In the next configuration, the TMDs are distributed with a linear variation as the shape of the first mode of vibration. Since it results in 25 different types of TMDs, they were grouped into five groups, each with 5 TMDs of the same properties (B1VLD0) and the heavier mass group is placed at the top. Since the top floors are those experiencing higher displacements and floor accelerations, the TMDs are distributed only to the top 20 floors with a total of 10 TMDs of the same properties (B1VTD0). For horizontal variations, the TMDs are distributed in the shape of a cross along the centreline axes of the building (B1H1D0) as they are assumed to undergo maximum displacements along the perimeter of the building (B1H2D0) in an attempt to preserve the core area of the building and throughout the plan area (B1H3D0) in the topmost storey of the building. For building B2, only horizontal variations are performed to study the effect of TMDs in torsional response. A single TMD is placed at the centre of the plan (B2S1D0) as in building B1, at the edge of the plan opposite to the position of concrete walls (B2S2D0) to prevent eccentric torsion and distributed along the perimeter of the building (B2S3D0) where the effect of torsional response is maximum. The TMDs are modelled in SAP2000 as a link with the properties as in Table 3 for all the configurations.

Table 3. Properties of TMDs in different configurations

Configurations	No. of TMDs	Mass (Kg)	Stiffness (N/m)	Mass ratio per TMD (%)
B1S0D0	0	-	-	-
B1S1D0	1	352340.64	932440.00	1.000
B1VCD0	25	14093.63	37397.60	0.040
B1VLD0	5	23489.38	62162.66	0.067
	5	18791.50	49730.13	0.053
	5	14093.63	37297.60	0.040
	5	9395.75	24865.07	0.027
	5	4697.88	12432.53	0.013
B1VTD0	10	35234.06	93244.00	0.100
B1H1D0	9	39148.96	103604.44	0.110
B1H2D0	16	22021.29	58277.50	0.063
B1H3D0	25	14093.63	37297.60	0.040
B2S0D0	0	-	-	-
B2S1D0	1	372223.50	1016504.00	1.000
B2S2D0	1	372223.50	1016504.00	1.000
B2S3D0	11	33838.50	92409.45	0.091

5 RESULTS FROM THE PRESENT STUDY

5.1 Comparison of structural performance

The response time histories in the form of displacement and acceleration at a node at the topmost storey of building B1 for all the simulated configurations are converted to the frequency domain in terms of power spectral density (PSD) and plotted in Fig. 4 - 5. The peaks of the responses in the form of PSD, displacement and acceleration are shown in Table 4. It is observed that the building with TMDs of constant mass and stiffness results in good displacement control, whereas no significant difference is seen in controlling the floor acceleration. In Fig. 6, it is seen that the performance of the single TMD configuration is less satisfactory. The responses of three different configurations of horizontal distributions and single TMD configuration are plotted, and found that there is no significant difference in performance among the three configurations in displacement and acceleration control.

Fig. 4. a) PSD comparison of displacement between building B1 and with a single TMD
 b) PSD comparison of acceleration between building B1 and with a single TMD

Fig. 5. a) PSD comparison of displacement between three vertical distribution configurations
 b) PSD comparison of displacement between best vertical configuration and single TMD

Since the presence of eccentric concrete walls in building B2 produces the torsional motion, the study is done for both the X and Y directions with the wind acting along the X direction. The responses are calculated at the corner node of the topmost storey in the direction opposite to the walls. The plots of PSD for responses along the X direction are shown in Fig. 6 – 7, and for the Y direction, they are shown in Fig. 8 – 9. In Fig. 6, the PSD of responses of the building without TMDs and with a single TMD at the centre are plotted. In Fig. 7, responses of all three configurations are plotted, and it is found that a single TMD at the edge opposite to the side of the walls performs better both in the case of displacement and acceleration control. Similarly, responses

for the Y direction are plotted in *Fig. 8* and *Fig. 9*, and it is observed that the same configuration performs the best in the Y direction, too.

Fig. 6. a) PSD comparison of X displacement between building B2 and with a single TMD
 b) PSD comparison of X acceleration between building B2 and with a single TMD

Fig. 7. a) PSD comparison of X displacement between horizontal distribution configurations
 b) PSD comparison of X acceleration between horizontal distribution configurations

Fig. 8. a) PSD comparison of Y displacement between building B2 and with a single TMD
 b) PSD comparison of Y acceleration between building B2 and with a single TMD

Fig. 9. a) PSD comparison of Y displacement between horizontal distribution configurations
 b) PSD comparison of Y acceleration between horizontal distribution configurations

It is evident that the buildings with a single-tuned mass damper perform much better than the base building B1 with a 72% reduction in peak PSD of displacement as well as acceleration, 7.5% reduction in peak displacement and 15% reduction in acceleration. However, the differences between the different horizontal configurations and vertical configurations are almost negligible compared to the single TMD structure in terms of displacement and acceleration, with B1VTD0 performing better in controlling acceleration. Hence, the number of values above a particular percentage of the peak value of the base building is counted and compared to get a better interpretation of the results. To get a significant amount of data for comparison, the bar is set at 60% of the peak of the base building for displacement and 30% for acceleration. Since the loading is applied suddenly at the initial position, higher values of acceleration are found at the initial 10 seconds. Hence, the initial acceleration data for 10 seconds are neglected. In this way, about a 28% reduction in the number of values is found between the base building and the building with a single TMD for displacement and 53.7% for acceleration. In comparison among the horizontal configurations with single TMD, no significant difference is observed, but with vertical configurations, B1VLD0 showed a 6% reduction in displacement.

Table 4. Peaks of responses of all the configurations

Configurations	Peak PSD (m ² /Hz)	Peak displacement (m)	No. of values above 60% of the peak of the base building	Peak PSD (m ² /s ⁴ /Hz)	Peak acceleration (m/s ²)	No. of values above 30% of the peak of the base building
B1S0D0	0.038	0.252	793	0.239	0.266	872
B1S1D0	0.0106	0.234	574	0.067	0.213	403
B1VCD0	0.009	0.237	568	0.067	0.216	422
B1VLD0	0.0125	0.236	544	0.061	0.213	406
B1VTD0	0.0145	0.235	577	0.067	0.184	420
B1H1D0	0.0106	0.234	574	0.067	0.215	399
B1H2D0	0.0106	0.234	575	0.067	0.215	403
B1H3D0	0.0106	0.234	577	0.067	0.215	401
B2S0D0 - x	0.057	0.287	787	0.441	0.33	833
B2S0D0 - y	4.6 E-3	0.077	414	0.036	0.108	2553
B2S1D0 - x	0.0176	0.269	551	0.108	0.218	364
B2S1D0 - y	1.25 E-3	0.075	206	0.010	0.083	2169
B2S2D0 - x	0.0162	0.265	544	0.083	0.234	292
B2S2D0 - y	1.12 E-3	0.074	230	0.007	0.098	2091
B2S3D0 - x	0.013	0.267	555	0.082	0.225	323
B2S3D0 - y	1.41 E-3	0.075	222	0.006	0.088	2105

From *Table 4*, it can be said that configuration B1VLD0 performs better in controlling displacement and configuration B1VTD0 for acceleration control in building B1. For building B2, the configuration B2S3D0 performs better in controlling displacement and the configuration B2S2D0 performs better in controlling displacement.

The performance of the different configurations can be compared overall by giving scores for displacement and acceleration separately. It considers all three parameters, such as peak PSD, peak displacement or acceleration and the number of values above a specific percentage of the peak value of the base building. The formulations for scoring are given in *Eq. (3-5)*. The overall performance score for displacement and acceleration response is given by *Eq. (6)*. The scores are listed in *Table 5*.

$$S_{psd} = \left(1 - \frac{\text{peak PSD} - \text{Min of peak PSD}}{\text{Min of peak PSD}} \right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$S_p = \left(1 - \frac{\text{peak response} - \text{Min of peak responses}}{\text{Min of peak responses}} \right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$S_{nv} = \left(1 - \frac{\text{No. of values} - \text{Min of no. of values}}{\text{Min of no. of values}} \right) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

$$S_d \text{ or } S_a = \left(\frac{S_{psd} + S_p + S_{nv}}{3} \right) \quad (6)$$

Table 5. Scores for displacement and acceleration control

Configurations	$S_{psd,d}$	$S_{p,d}$	$S_{nv,d}$	S_d	$S_{psd,a}$	$S_{p,a}$	$S_{nv,a}$	S_a
B1S1D0	82.2	100	94.5	92.2	90.2	84.2	99	91.1
B1VCD0	100	98.7	95.6	98.1	90.2	82.6	94.2	89
B1VLD0	61.1	99	100	86.7	100	84.2	98.2	94.1
B1VTD0	38.9	99.5	93.9	77.4	90.2	100	94.7	95
B1H1D0	82.2	100	94.5	92.2	90.2	83.1	100	91.1
B1H2D0	82.2	100	94.3	92.2	90.2	83.1	99	90.8
B1H3D0	82.2	100	93.9	92	90.2	83.1	99.5	90.9
B2S1D0 – x	64.6	98.5	98.7	87.3	68.3	100	75.3	81.2
B2S1D0 – y	88.4	98.6	100	95.7	33.3	100	96.3	76.5
B2S2D0 – x	75.4	100	100	91.8	98.8	92.7	100	97.2
B2S2D0 – y	100	100	88.4	96.1	83.3	81.9	100	88.4
B2S3D0 – x	100	99.2	97.9	99	100	96.8	89.4	95.4
B2S3D0 – y	74.1	98.6	92.2	88.3	100	93.9	99.3	97.7

5.2 Comparison of area required for installation and their efficacy

The additional parameters considered in this research are the area required for installation and efficacy of MTMD. Increasing the count of TMDs decreases the usable area inside the building, which affects the economy, but the efficacy increases. In this context, efficacy denotes that there is no significant effect in the damping of the building due to the sudden failure or any unusable condition of any TMD, which might have several reasons, like poor maintenance or others. For a single TMD structure, the sudden unavailability of TMD means the building suddenly becomes almost an undamped structure and causes lots of discomfort to the people inside the building. Using multiple TMDs helps increase the efficacy as other TMDs operate even if one becomes non-functional, ensuring smooth serviceability. The scores for the configurations considering both these factors are shown in *Table 6*. The area used by one TMD is assumed to be one panel of slab area (25 m²), and the score is calculated by *Eq. (7)*. The risk of failure is calculated by *Eq. (8)*, and the score for efficacy is calculated by *Eq. (9)*.

$$S_{au} = \left(\frac{\text{Max area used by TMDs} - \text{Area used}}{\text{Max area used by TMDs}} \right) \times 100 \quad (7)$$

$$Risk = \frac{100}{No. of TMDs} \quad (8)$$

$$S_r = \left(\frac{Max\ risk - Risk}{Max\ risk} \right) \times 100 \quad (9)$$

Table 6. Scores for area usage and efficacy

Configurations	No. of dampers	Area used (m ²)	S_{au}	Risk (%)	S_r
B1S1D0	1	25	96	100	0
B1VCD0	25	625	0	4	96
B1VLD0	25	625	0	4	96
B1VTD0	10	250	60	10	90
B1H1D0	9	225	64	11.11	88.89
B1H2D0	16	400	36	6.25	93.75
B1H3D0	25	625	0	4	96
B2S1D0	1	25	90.9	100	0
B2S2D0	1	25	90.9	100	0
B2S3D0	11	275	0	9.09	90.91

5.3 Overall performance comparison

The overall scoring for all the above configurations is given by Eq. (10). Four different constants are introduced in this equation which are the weightages assigned to each of these parameters. In this research, we have considered 30% weightage for displacement control, 30% for acceleration control, 25% for area usage and 15% for risk factor, hence accounting for around 60% for structural performance and 40% for economy. The overall scores are listed in Table 7. It can be interpreted that the configuration B1H1D0 has been the best considering all these parameters for building B1, and the configuration B2S2D0 has been the best for building B2. Based on the necessity, the weightages can be altered, or any parameter can even be neglected, too, as per the situation. For example, if the displacement control is not a necessary parameter, the configuration B1VTD0 is found to be advantageous, and if the area usage parameter is neglected, B1VCD0 performs better than the rest for building B1.

$$S = \eta_d S_d + \eta_a S_a + \eta_{au} S_{au} + \eta_r S_r \quad (10)$$

Table 7. Overall Scores for all configurations

Configurations	S_d	S_a	S_{au}	S_r	S
B1S1D0	92.2	91.1	96	0	79
B1VCD0	98.1	89	0	96	70.5
B1VLD0	86.7	94.1	0	96	68.6
B1VTD0	77.4	95	60	90	80.2
B1H1D0	92.2	91.1	64	88.89	84.3
B1H2D0	92.2	90.8	36	93.75	78
B1H3D0	92	90.9	0	96	69.3
B2S1D0 - x	87.3	81.2			73.3
B2S1D0 - y	95.7	76.5	90.9	0	74.4
B2S2D0 - x	91.8	97.2			79.4
B2S2D0 - y	96.1	88.4	90.9	0	78.1
B2S3D0 - x	99	95.4			72
B2S3D0 - y	88.3	97.7	0	90.91	69.4

6 CONCLUSIONS

To the author's knowledge, among several works, the present paper investigated the effect of multiple undamped tuned mass dampers in two different steel tall buildings. The wind velocity fluctuation time histories, generated by NatHaz Online Web Simulator, are converted to wind force time history for the Chennai location. One of the buildings has a bisymmetric cross-section, and the

other has an eccentric concrete shear wall at an edge parallel to the direction of wind loading. Tuned mass dampers, an efficient device in damping out wind-induced oscillations, also carry disadvantages like installing a big mass at a single point of the building, sudden reduction in damping of the building during maintenance issues in TMD, etc. Hence, the concept of multiple-tuned mass dampers evolved, and this study investigates the parameters like the different types of variations in the distribution of TMDs, the area required for their installation, and their efficacy when one of the TMDs becomes non-functional. It is found that the configuration of distributing the TMDs horizontally in the shape of a cross (B1H1D0) has been the most effective configuration considering all the above-considered parameters, clearly 5% better score than the following best configuration of vertical distribution in the top few floors (B1VTD0) for building B1 and the single TMD configuration installed at the edge opposite to the edge where concrete shear walls (B2S2D0) performs better by around 10% than the configuration with TMDs distribution along the perimeter for building B2. The necessity to consider all these parameters might not be there for every practical case because if the lateral displacements of the building are already in control and the floor acceleration exceeds the codal limits, the score for displacement parameter can be neglected, and the configuration with TMDs only at the top 20 storeys (B1VCD0) will perform the best. Suppose there is another choice of going for aerodynamic shapes where the reduction in the plan area of the building would be higher. In that case, the score for the area parameter can be neglected, and in such a case, the configuration with TMDs of constant mass and stiffness throughout the height of the building (B1VTD0) would be the optimal solution. Hence it is the decision of the engineer-in-charge to decide the parameters and their weightages to be considered for the best performance of the building structurally as well as economically.

REFERENCES

1. Council on Tall Buildings and Urban Habitat. [Online] CTBUH. [Cited: February 11, 2024.] <https://www.ctbuh.org/resource/height>.
2. Bureau of Indian Standards. Criteria for structural safety of tall concrete buildings. IS 16700 : 2023.
3. *Seismic Control of Tall Buildings Using Distributed Multiple Tuned Mass Dampers*. Radmard Rahmani, Hamid and Konke, Carsten. s.l. : Hindawi Ltd, 2019, Vol. 2019. 6480384.
4. *Wind-induced Aerodynamic Instability of Super-tall Buildings with Various Cross-sectional Shapes*. Kim, Wonsul, Yoshida, Akihito and Tamura, Yukio. 4, s.l. : International Journal of High-Rise Building, 2019, Vol. 8.
5. *Revisiting the "T" in TMD*. Strobel, Kurt and Salcedo, Victor. 2, s.l. : International Journal of High-Rise Buildings, 2021, Vol. 10.
6. Connor, Jerome J. and La, Simon. *Structural Motion Engineering*. s.l. : Springer Cham, 2014. 978-3-319-06280-8.
7. *Listing of installations*. Holmes, J, D. 9, s.l. : Journal of Engineering Structures, 1995, Vol. 17. 0141-0296.
8. *Optimal tuned mass-damper-inerter (TMDI) design in wind-excited tall*. Petrini, Francesco, Giaralis, Agathokolis and Wang, Zixiao. s.l. : Journal of Engineering Structures, 2020, Vol. 204. 18737323.
9. *Effect of multiple tuned mass dampers for vibration control in high rise buildings*. Suresh, Lekshmi and Mini, K. M. 4, s.l. : American Society of Civil Engineers, 2019, Vol. 24. 1084-0680.
10. *Wind-induced vibration control of tall buildings by designing the overhead fire water tanks as compliant deep tank dampers-inerter*. Das, Anupam, Konar, Tanmoy and Banerjee, Arnab. s.l. : Structures, 2023, Vol. 58. 23520124.
11. *e-Analysis of High-Rise Buildings Subjected to Wind Loads*. Kwon, D., Kijewski-Correa, T and Kareem, A. 7, s.l. : Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE), 2008, Vol. 133.
12. *Simulation of multicorrelated random processes using the FFT algorithm*. Wittig, L. E and Sinha, A. K. 3, s.l. : Acoustical Society of America (ASA), 1975, Vol. 58. 0001-4966.
13. Bureau of Indian Standards. Design load (other than earthquake) for buildings and structures. IS 875 Part 3 : 2015.